

Design and Performance Analysis of a High-assay Low Enriched Uranium-fueled Bimodal Nuclear Thermal Rocket

Simon Hatcher ^{1,*}, Nathaniel Read¹

¹University of Cambridge, Department of Engineering, Trumpington St., Cambridge CB2 1PZ, UK

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ABSTRACT

Human and robotic spaceflight beyond the Earth and Moon will require the application of novel technologies to achieve the high thrust and propulsive efficiency necessary for repeated orbital maneuvers. Proposed bimodal nuclear thermal electric propulsion (BNTEP) systems use a shared core to heat a propellant gas for nuclear thermal propulsion (NTP) and to generate electricity for nuclear electric propulsion (NEP). The combination of these technologies, in conjunction with electric thrusters, allows significant reduction in transit time for a notional mission to Mars. This project proposes a bimodal nuclear thermal rocket (BNTR) core, based on a variant of the tested Pewee nuclear thermal rocket fueled by high-assay low-enriched uranium, which modifies the moderator element design to include distinct channels for a helium-xenon (He-Xe) closed Brayton cycle power mode. To capture the coupled relationship between the neutronic and thermal-hydraulic (T/H) solutions in the core, a coupled framework is developed which interfaces Serpent Monte-Carlo neutronic solutions with coreThM, a reduced-order T/H solver. The T/H solution is verified using finite element analysis. The theoretical performance of the NTP and NEP systems in their respective propulsion and power operating modes is characterized. A burnup analysis is conducted to assess the performance of the core over the full duration of a notional mission with multiple burns and sustained midcourse operation. A final design configuration for a BNTR core is proposed which generates 50 kW_e per engine with no adverse impact on NTP performance.

Keywords: NTP, NEP, Thermohydraulics, Multiphysics, Neutronics

1. INTRODUCTION

The efficacies of existing chemical and electric space propulsion methods are bounded by immutable constraints on propellant molecular mass and thrust, respectively. Two methods which show near-term promise for increasing propulsive efficiency at high power are nuclear thermal propulsion (NTP) and nuclear electric propulsion (NEP). NTP system designs under development employ a reactor core to heat propellant gases, achieving a vacuum specific impulse (I_{sp}) value of approximately 875-950 s, about twice the 450 s achieved by conventional chemical rockets at similar thrust outputs. NEP systems use a nuclear reactor to generate electrical power for electric thrusters, which deliver much higher I_{sp} but lower thrust than nuclear thermal rockets (NTRs), making them well-suited to midcourse corrections and long-duration burns.

A potential fusion of these two technologies is the bimodal nuclear thermal electric propulsion (BNTEP) system, which combines the NTR reactor core with a power cycle to generate electrical power for NEP when NTP is not active. This excess energy can be extracted, when the NTR is not in use, in a closed thermodynamic cycle. The notional BNTEP system offers both the high thrust power and high I_{sp} of the NTR for short impulsive maneuvers and the extremely high I_{sp} of NEP with significant mass savings from the shared reactor. Additionally, it offers electrical power for habitation, spacecraft systems (including maintaining propellant at cryogenic temperatures), and science missions without dependence on large photovoltaic arrays [1].

*sah246@cam.ac.uk

1.1. Prior Work

20th-century Nuclear Engine for Rocket Vehicle Applications (NERVA) program testing employed strictly highly enriched uranium (HEU)-fueled cores; the physics of high-assay low enriched uranium (HALEU) NTR cores remain experimentally uncharacterized. With stringent restrictions on ground testing of open-cycle reactor designs such as NTRs, recent engineering efforts have depended heavily upon the use of computational numerical methods for neutronic, thermal-hydraulic (T/H), radiological, and mechanical analysis of SNP designs.

Neutronic analysis studies of NTRs in recent years have favored the use of codes like Serpent and MCNP, continuous energy Monte-Carlo method-based neutron transport codes, which have been verified and validated and allow easy integration into frameworks for multiphysics simulations [2]. However, it is insufficient to calculate the reactor flux and power distribution from an approximated reactor temperature and coolant density field; there are strong temperature and density feedback mechanisms which drive the flux profile. It is thus necessary to characterize coolant fluid dynamics and heat transfer within fuel element (FE) propellant gas channels, moderator element (ME) cooling channels, and (in the case of the proposed BNTR design) the dynamics of the He-Xe coolant channels. Numerous studies have employed various approaches of various fidelities to NTP T/H simulation [3].

2. METHODS

2.1. Design

The developed core modifies the design outlined by [4] for a NERVA-derived HALEU-fueled NTR design with 330 MW_T power in propulsion mode. The core radial cross-section is shown in Figure 1.

The FE design (red in Figure 1) is a ceramic-ceramic (CERCER) type with uranium nitride (UN)-HALEU fuel kernels in a zirconium carbide (ZrC) matrix. UN is enriched to 19.75%, and variable fuel kernel loading is employed across the core to reduce power peaking.

The NTR design is modified by the addition of three dual-pass He-Xe channels (shown in dark and light yellow for supply and return, respectively), clad in ZrC, to the moderator matrix (isotropic graphite, shown in burnt orange in Figures 1 and 2). The He-Xe channels are designed to operate in both power mode and propulsion mode so that power to the spacecraft can be supplied continuously. Dual-pass power cycle channels were initially selected to avoid complicating the core exit manifold and support plate, which is exposed to high temperatures in propulsion operation. A U-bend at the base of the ME turns the He-Xe flow from each supply channel to its return channel; the neutronic impact of this U-bend geometry is not modeled.

A layer of porous ZrC (gray), selected for its low thermal conductivity, insulates the Inconel 718 outer tie tube (white) from the graphite matrix. The annular channel (blue) between the outer tie tube and the ZrH moderator (green) is the return passage for H₂ coolant in the ME. Inside the ZrH, the Inconel 718 inner tie tube (white) encloses the supply passage for H₂ coolant in the ME (blue).

A beryllium oxide (BeO) radial reflector (shown in purple) surrounds the core; reactivity control is accomplished with BeO control drums with a 0.5 cm-thickness 40% boron-10-enriched poison vein on one side (pink), shown here rotated fully outwards. A 10 cm-thickness BeO axial reflector sits atop

Figure 1. BNTR core radial cross-section [4].

Figure 2. Close-up radial cross-sections for FE (right) and ME (left) for modified design.

the core. Penetrations of the axial reflector for He-Xe channels, tie tube cooling channels, and FE H_2 channels are neglected, as is the neutronic impact of support plates below the core. The dry mass of the core is 2534 kg [4]. For power cycle operation without NTP, an identical geometry is considered, but with no H_2 in MEs or FEs. These materials are replaced in the Serpent geometry definition with voids. A series of He-Xe channel configurations for single-pass and dual-pass flow were tested to minimize temperature peaking in the ME and ensure a uniform intra-element outlet temperature.

2.2. Serpent solver

The input file for the Serpent solver is programmatically generated in each design iteration to facilitate easy modification of the solver settings, core dimensions, and material properties. The reduced-order coreThM code is used for T/H feedback and has been verified against higher-order methods for exactly analogous geometries, including for the inverse-Pewee which forms the basis of this BNTR [5, 4]. The coreThM and Serpent codes are coupled and iterated until neutronic solution convergence. Serpent interface files for H_2 in the moderator supply and return and fuel channels, He-Xe supply and return channels, fuel, graphite, and ZrH specify spatial variation in temperature and density in these materials, as these materials have strong density gradients or temperature-driven neutronic cross-section variation. Material properties are obtained from [6]. For this analysis, hydrogen loss from the ZrH moderator is neglected; this is recognized as an assumption which future analysis must model.

By default, Serpent only models power deposition in the material containing fissile isotopes; this setting is modified to account for deposition via elastic scattering and absorption in moderator materials. Power for the entire core is normalized to 330 MW_T in propulsion mode and 150 kW_T in power mode.

2.3. Finite element analysis solver

A custom 3-D FEA solver is constructed in Python for the supercell geometry for high-fidelity T/H analysis. The solver is built on the Simple Finite Element in Python (SFEPy) package combined with a separately-designed correlation-based fluid flow solver [7].

3. RESULTS

3.1. Neutronic solution

The iterative solver is used to develop a converged N+T/H solution for both propulsion and power modes. To avoid excessive thermal stress on single elements and ensure uniform propellant and He-Xe outlet temperatures through the core, it is desirable to maintain uniform element powers. Radial peaking is influenced by both operating mode and control drum position. With the poison veins rotated fully outwards (180°), peripheral elements are in close proximity to the BeO reflector, and power peaking is low. When rotated inwards, poison veins near the peripheral elements depress the flux in this region, increasing power peaking. This presents another challenge for the differential control drum positions required for the different operating modes. The effect of control drum position on maximum and minimum radial power peaking factor is shown in Figure 3. For most drum settings, the differ-

Figure 3. Beginning-of-life k_{eff} (left) and power peaking factors (right) for power and propulsion operating modes, varying drum angle. Core global minima and maxima for both modes are included.

ence between maximum and minimum power peaking factors for power operation is less than that of propulsion operation. This is a consequence of the hardened spectrum in power operation; the core is undermoderated in this mode, as no H_2 is present.

A similar trend is observed in the plot of k_{eff} with respect to control drum position. Initially, the reactivity impact of drum withdrawal is low, then peaks near 90° (as the projected area of the poison facing the core decreases most rapidly), then decreases again. This is consistent with prior studies. At high drum angles, relatively little reactivity difference is observed between the two modes at the same drum settings. At its peak, linearized drum rotation reactivity worth is $0.096 \text{ } \$/\text{degree}$ outwards. Total drum reactivity worth in propulsion mode is 7518 pcm , or $11.75 \text{ } \$$, and in power mode is 9095 pcm , or $14.21 \text{ } \$$. There is thus sufficient excess reactivity to operate in both power and propulsion modes in the fresh core (in steady state) despite the aforementioned peaking challenges. Additionally, a full burnup analysis was conducted for a notional BNTEP Mars mission; burnup is low (1.1 MWd/kg), and drum worth is sufficient to counteract reactivity decrease from depletion. Transient operation is not treated in this work, and may yet pose challenges with insufficient shutdown margin or excess reactivity; future work will explore cold zero-power characteristics of the BNTR design and reactivity temperature coefficients.

3.2. Propulsion mode T/H solution

The temperature profile in propulsion mode operation is strongly driven by the temperature profile in the FE, which is the hottest solid material, shown in Figure 4. The limiting temperature in propulsion

Figure 4. FEA solver fluid and solid solutions in centermost (9.9 vol-% loading, at left) and outermost (28.8 vol-% loading, at right) FEs. Cladding and channel bulk solutions are for centermost propellant channel; fuel maximum is maximum temperature in each FE axial bin.

mode operation is typically the melting temperature of UN kernels in the FE, about 3120 K [8]. The FEA supercell solution is generated for interior (9.9 vol-% UN loading) and exterior (28.8 vol-% UN loading) elements to compare the solutions across the core. Supercell global maxima relative to limits for each material are described in Table I below. UN maintains a safety margin of over 250 K from

Table I. Maximum global temperatures of core solid materials relative to temperature limits in propulsion mode.

Material	Material plot label	Limiting temperature (K) [reason][source]	Innermost supercell. FE #1 is 9.9 vol-% loading, FE #2 is 10.2 vol-% loading.		Outermost supercell. FE #1 is 28.8 vol-% loading, FE #2 is 23.4 vol-% loading.	
			Global maximum temperature (K)	Fraction of limiting temperature	Global maximum temperature (K)	Fraction of limiting temperature
ZrC channel clad in FE #1	Feclad1	3800 [melting][9]	2834 ²	0.746	2829	0.744
ZrC channel clad in FE #2	Feclad2	3800 [melting][9] ¹	2835	0.746	2831	0.745
UN-ZrC in FE #1	Fuel1	3120 [UN melting][8] ²	2853	0.914	2843	0.911
UN-ZrC in FE #2	Fuel2	3120 [UN melting][8] ²	2854	0.915	2849	0.913
Graphite tie matrix	Graph1	>3500 [melting][10] ³	2769	0.791	2694	0.770
ZrC He-Xe channel cladding	Hexeclad	3800 [melting][9] ¹	2692	0.708	2616	0.688
Inconel 718 in inner tie tube	Innertie	1530 [melting][11] ⁴	543	0.355	474	0.310
Inconel 718 in outer tie tube	Outertie	1530 [melting][11] ⁴	917	0.599	878	0.574
Porous ME ZrC insulator	Zrc	3800 [melting][9] ¹	2612	0.687	2541	0.669
ZrH moderator	Zrh	1020 [H diffusion][12] ⁵	595	0.583	526	0.516

its limiting temperature. All other materials have substantial safety margins in propulsion mode. The ZrH moderator has the lowest maximum temperature of any core material, but is maintained at low temperatures by cryogenic H₂ flow in the ME channels.

3.3. Power mode T/H solution

Similar temperature limits and profiles are considered for power mode operation. Once again, the FEA solution is generated for interior and exterior supercells to compare results throughout the core. Initially, the same inlet conditions for He-Xe operation are employed. The temperature profiles for the two studied He-Xe flow configurations are shown in Figure 5. The centermost supercell is shown, as this has the highest FE power and thus is where material temperature limits are most likely to be exceeded.

Figure 5. FEA axial bulk He-Xe channel temperature profile solutions for single-pass (left) and dual-pass (right) He-Xe channels in power operation mode for innermost supercell (9.9 vol-% loading). Note flow reversal of He-Xe flow at core bottom ($z = 120$ cm) from supply into return channels.

The axial profile of bulk He-Xe temperatures in the single pass case is straightforward and as expected, rising uniformly from exit to entrance, slightly exceeding the desired 1150 K turbine inlet temperature. The dual-pass case presents a significant challenge. Here, He-Xe enters the core at 970 K and is immediately heated by the hotter surrounding elements. As it flows down towards the core bottom ($z = 120$ cm), it continues absorbing heat until reaching a maximum temperature at the core bottom. It turns into the FE-adjacent return channels and returns to the core top, losing heat via conduction to the cooler materials surrounding it before being expelled at approximately 1150 K, the desired turbine inlet temperature. As a result, the fluid heating process is inefficient. The He-Xe flowing back to the top of the core ($z = 0$) through the return channel exit is losing heat to its own supply channel through conduction. The He-Xe bulk temperature drives the axial profiles in all of the solid components in both channel configurations.

The inner tie (1587 K maximum), outer tie (1592 K), and ZrH (1592 K) significantly exceed their temperature limits throughout the whole core in the dual-pass design configuration. The simple addition of dual-pass tubes in the ME is thus grossly inadequate to allow operation of the core in power mode. The single-pass design reduces maximum moderator temperatures to 1189 K, a substantial improvement over the dual-pass case. The single-pass solution at the original inlet temperature of 970 K remains insufficient to reduce ZrH temperatures to within limits; it is thus pursued in conjunction with a reduction in core inlet temperature to 700 K for the final recommended configuration. The turbine inlet (core outlet) temperature in power mode is decreased to 890 K from the original desired value of 1150 K. This has attendant implications for cycle efficiency, described below.

4. ANALYSIS, CONCLUSIONS, AND FUTURE WORK

The performance of the notional bimodal system is calculated based on the characteristics of the BNTR core. The propulsion system I_{sp} is calculated straightforwardly given the chamber exit temperature (2720 K) to be 899.6 s. This is almost exactly the 900–910 s cited by other designs, and twice the performance of state-of-the-art vacuum chemical rockets [13]. The thrust per engine is 67.8 kN; this is typical of new, HALEU-fueled low power density NTRs, and, for three engines, is comparable to or exceeds the thrust provided by chemical upper stages [14].

Power mode operation is assessed with relations from [15]. Brayton cycle thermal efficiency is reduced by the final design from 31% at a 1150 K turbine inlet to approximately 23% for a 900 K turbine inlet [15]. For the same thermal power, the reactor then generates 34.5 kW_e, or 104 kW_e total. Heat rejection (and thus radiator mass) requirements increase as well. To achieve the original desired power of 150 kW_e, the BNTRs must be uprated to 217 kW_T each, and radiators must reject an additional 202 kW_T of waste heat over the base design. [16] find total specific mass for a NEP radiator design of 6.1 kg/m², including structural and flow circulation components. The efficiency reduction then translates to a dry mass increase of 850 kg, a significant mass penalty.

A counteracting benefit of the BNTR system is the ability to remove decay heat while conserving H₂ propellant. NTR designs require the expulsion (without propulsive benefit) of significant quantities of H₂ propellant gas to remove decay heat after NTP shutdown until power levels drop such that radiative heat transfer to space is sufficient to cool the core. Use of power mode operation could reduce decay heat removal H₂ mass requirements without additional system mass. A coarse lumped estimate is used to briefly estimate this benefit using the widely-employed Wigner-Way formula for reactor decay heat [17]. For three clustered BNTR engines and four NTP burns studied for a notional Mars mission, 1.33 tons of H₂ propellant can be conserved, which begets significant efficiency gains in mission planning (and outweighs the radiator mass penalty). This is likely an underestimate given the poor heat rejection of the bare NTR casing and cumulative waste heat rejection requirements from late-mission burns.

This analysis highlights some of the benefits and challenges inherent in bimodal operation via full-core coupled N+T/H modeling. The addition of tie tube He-Xe channels to NERVA-type geometry for a power operating mode is fundamentally constrained by temperature limits in the moderator components. The moderator volume required in a thermal-spectrum HALEU BNTR makes thermal isolation of the moderator material from the FEs and power cycle channels a significant challenge. The best strategy for BNTR design with high-TRL materials is a single-pass configuration with a reduced He-Xe outlet temperature. The proposed single-pass BNTR modification to the inverse-Pewee design generates 150 kW_e across three engines without impacting performance in NTP.

One outstanding design challenge is the configuration of the outlet He-Xe plenum for single-pass Brayton fluid channels. This must be capable of withstanding the high temperatures and pressures (2700 K and 7 MPa) of the BNTR chamber and avoid causing form losses or flow obstructions at the FE propellant channel exits. He-Xe flow paths out of the ME channels and into the plenum ducts could lead to additional pressure losses, heating, or cooling effects which are not considered here.

Notwithstanding these, a HALEU-fueled high-power BNTR is feasible from a neutronic and thermal-hydraulic perspective. Bimodal nuclear propulsion offers speed and flexibility to outer-space mission designs which are unattainable via chemical rockets or unimodal SNP. Their continued development will be a significant boon to future space exploration.

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